

PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE PRESCHOOL EDUCATORS IN THE FIELD OF ARTISTIC-AESTHETIC EDUCATION THROUGH CONTEXTUAL TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *This article discusses the specifics of developing subject-specific artistic competence among future preschool educators in the field of artistic-aesthetic education using contextual teaching technologies. The students mentioned in this study were observed during the classes on "Visual Arts Education".*

Keywords: *professional training, future preschool educators, contextual teaching technologies.*

Objective of the article – to reveal the methodology for integrating contextual learning technologies into the process of preparing future preschool educators and to experimentally test their effectiveness in the field of artistic-aesthetic education for children.

The research utilized methods such as analysis and synthesis of psychological-pedagogical and artistic sources, as well as the study and generalization of the current state of professional training of future preschool educators in the field of artistic-aesthetic education. Additionally, the analysis and comparison of the levels of subject-specific competence of future preschool educators in artistic-aesthetic education were employed.

The results of the experiment demonstrated the necessity of implementing contextual learning technologies in the development of subject-specific competence among future preschool educators in the field of artistic-aesthetic education.

Introduction

Contextual learning technologies include a system of didactic forms, methods, and tools that model the substantive and social content of a specialist's future professional activities. At the same time, the foundation of these activities lies in the acquisition of knowledge and the development of competencies.

The primary goal of contextual learning technologies is to ensure the proactive nature of personal activity, which contributes to the development of the necessary subject-specific, professional, and social qualities of a specialist.

Contextual educational technologies create conditions for the integration of learning and future professional activities as one of the ways to achieve professional competence.

The aim of these technologies is to embed the educational process into the context of future professional activities by introducing real connections and relationships into various forms and methods of teaching provided by higher education institutions. This also involves solving specific professional tasks that require the development of a range of specialized competencies.

Contextual technologies in the professional training of educators are characterized by aspects such as shifting the focus from the teaching activity of university instructors to the cognitive activity, work, and engagement of students.

The main parameter of a contextual-type educational process is the modeling of the substantive and social content of future professional activities through the reproduction of real professional situations.

The main forms of contextual learning include academic-type educational activities (lectures, practical sessions, independent work); quasi-professional activities (business games, role-playing learning forms); and educational-professional activities (research work, internships).

Modern scientific and pedagogical research explores various aspects of the professional training of students specializing in 60110200 – "Preschool Education." However, the issue of developing the subject-specific competence of future preschool educators in the artistic and aesthetic education of children through contextual educational technologies remains insufficiently studied.

The subject-specific artistic competence of future preschool educators refers to the ability to apply professionally-oriented artistic knowledge, skills, and competencies that form the theoretical and practical-technological foundation of the educational domain "The Child in the World of Culture", which is part of the core component of preschool education as a whole and its individual elements in particular.

Various components of subject-specific artistic competence in future preschool educators are identified, including musical, visual arts, artistic, and synthetic competencies.

The aim of this research is to identify the features of implementing contextual learning technologies in the training process of future preschool educators in the field of artistic and aesthetic education during the classes on "Teaching Visual Arts".

Materials and Methods

The study involved second-year students majoring in 60110200 – "Preschool Education." A total of 175 students participated in the experiment, with 73 in the experimental group and 102 in the control group.

The professional training of the control group students was conducted using traditional teaching methods in higher education institutions. This primarily consisted of lecture-based instruction, including lectures, practical sessions, and various forms of independent, individual, and research work by students. All participants provided informed consent prior to taking part in the study.

To address the research objectives, the following methods were employed:

Theoretical-scientific methods: analysis and synthesis of psychological-pedagogical and artistic sources, as well as internet resources.

Empirical methods: tests, interviews, surveys, expert evaluations, and a pedagogical experiment with qualitative and quantitative analysis of the results.

The pedagogical conditions of the experimental methodology included a system of activities:

Creating an innovative environment for the professional training of "Preschool Education" students in artistic and aesthetic activities under conditions that closely resembled their future professional and pedagogical roles.

Implementing organizational-methodological innovations to develop specific components of the subject-specific artistic competence of future preschool educators. These innovations encompassed various printed and video materials, as well as electronic and multimedia resources,

reference and information systems, educational programs for reinforcing knowledge, and assessment programs aimed at evaluating completed work.

An innovation-pedagogical orientation in the content of academic-methodological and art-related disciplines in higher education, incorporating contextual-pedagogical technologies into the discipline of methodology of teaching visual arts.

Implementation of Contextual Learning Technologies

The implementation of contextual learning technologies was carried out in three stages: **informational-operational, activity-technological, and reflective-creative.**

The goal of this stage was to provide future preschool educators with an understanding of their future profession, the specifics of artistic and aesthetic education for preschoolers, and the system of psychological-pedagogical, methodological, and artistic knowledge. This included developing practical artistic-creative competencies and mastering artistic techniques.

The objective of this stage was to develop the ability of future preschool educators to implement the functions of artistic and aesthetic education in real preschool teaching. This involved mastering general pedagogical and specialized artistic technologies and employing unconventional creative approaches.

To achieve this goal, an optimal combination of theoretical and practical components was developed to prepare students in the program 60110200 – "Preschool Education" for artistic and aesthetic education. This combination enabled them to acquire general professional competencies (pedagogical, psychological, methodological, and artistic) during visual arts classes.

Contextual tasks included:

Designing lesson plans with elements of game modeling in the artistic-aesthetic cycle.

Creating lesson plans that integrate music and art education.

Preparing and presenting art projects aimed at fostering children's cultural understanding of art.

Developing computer presentations, open learning formats, interactive video materials, texts, and multimedia packages.

The goal of this stage was to develop the ability of future educators to reflect on their professional experience and enhance their skills in artistic and aesthetic education within a preschool setting.

This goal was achieved by stabilizing and adjusting the already-formed psychological-pedagogical, methodological, and artistic knowledge and skills of students in the program 60110200 – "Preschool Education". It also involved fostering an individual professional style in artistic and aesthetic education, developing self-assessment and evaluation abilities, and strengthening independent research skills.

At this stage, a series of workshops was organized focusing on traditional folk arts and crafts, utilizing productive-creative technologies in visual arts.

At the conclusion of the experiment, a positive trend in the improvement of subject-specific competence was observed among the students in the experimental group, while the changes in the control group were less significant. The results of the final assessment demonstrated that in the experimental group, where intensive educational technologies were applied, statistically significant shifts occurred, indicating an overall increase in the professional readiness of future educators for artistic-pedagogical activities.

Conclusions

The positive dynamics observed in the development of subject-specific competence among future educators in the field of artistic and aesthetic education confirms the effectiveness of implementing contextual learning technologies. It can be concluded that the training process for future educators in preschool educational organizations can be enhanced through the consistent integration of contextual technologies such as modeling, simulation games, masterclasses, and creative workshops.

The results of the experimental work indicate positive improvements in the constructive, productive, and creative levels of students in the experimental group.

A clear positive trend was identified in the enhancement of professional training levels among the students of the experimental group. In contrast, the changes in the control group were less significant. These outcomes mark a positive result overall.

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